

FAILURE OF SOLID AND HOLLOW S2-GLASS FIBRE/EPOXY THICK TUBES UNDER BIAXIAL COMPRESSION

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SUMMARY

A comparative study is made of the biaxial compressive response of five tubes of different composite materials (solid and hollow fibre S2-glass/epoxy, E-glass/epoxy, T700 carbon/epoxy and Tenax carbon/epoxy). The specimens were $\pm 55^\circ$ angle-ply thick filament wound tubes which were tested to destruction under combined external radial pressure and axial compression that gave a nominal circumferential to axial stress ratio of -2:-1, commonly encountered in submersibles. Depending upon the material tested, it was necessary to test tubes with radius to thickness ratios R/h down to 2.8 in order to avoid structural instability and obtain material crushing, especially for the hollow fibre tubes. The specific compressive strength (strength/weight) obtained from the hollow glass tubes was observed to be comparable with those from the solid glass/tubes. The carbon fibre reinforced materials were superior to the glass fibre composites.

1. INTRODUCTION

Interest is growing in off-shore and other industries to find materials with high specific strength and stiffness suitable for making deep under water structures (e.g. Remotely Operated Vehicles and oil risers) that are generally subjected to hydrostatic pressure loading, Stevenson et al [1]. Fibre reinforced composite materials are an obvious option. Kaddour et al [2] tested $\pm 55^\circ$ filament wound thick cylinders made of E-glass/epoxy material under external pressure loading conditions. Graham [3] also reported some results showing the potential of $\pm 55^\circ$ filament wound carbon fibre epoxy in making cylindrical composite hulls. Efforts are being made to explore the feasibility of using other composite materials for deep-underwater applications. Hollow fibres and hollow fibre reinforced plastic composites are relatively a new class of materials that has been receiving growing interest over the last 5 years. Due to their light weight and electromagnetically transmissive properties, hollow fibre composites were shown to be attractive for use in certain aerospace applications, see Schuster and Harman [4].

A few investigations have been made to characterise the mechanical properties of hollow fibres composites. Schuster and Harman [4] provided some data on uniaxial tensile, compressive and

shear properties of unidirectional Hollex S2-glass fibres composites. Boniface et al [5] carried out tests on unidirectional and multidirectional ($\pm 45^\circ/0^\circ$), hollow and solid S2-glass/epoxy coupons to obtain the uniaxial tensile and compressive properties

Up to now, there appears to be no published data at all on the biaxial compressive behaviour of hollow fibre composites. Indeed, investigations into the biaxial compressive behaviour of fibre reinforced composites in general are limited. Most of the biaxial compressive test results reported previously did not represent material failure or crushing as buckling rather than crushing mode of failure prevailed. Kaddour et al [2] studied the crushing strength of $\pm 55^\circ$ E-glass/epoxy tubes under a large number of biaxial compression stress ratios. It was found that the highest failure strength was at a hoop to axial stress ratio around $-2/-1$, which is most familiar in submersibles subjected to external pressure. The strength under this biaxial compressive loading was considerably greater than when the cylinders were loaded under uniaxial compression.

The present work aims at comparing the performance of $\pm 55^\circ$ angle ply tubes of five different materials, under hydrostatic pressure. Effects of wall thickness on the failure stresses are shown both experimentally and theoretically.

2. EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS

2.1. Materials:

Filament wound tubes and unidirectional coupons were produced by the Structural Materials Centre (DERA, Fort Halstead, UK). The fibres used were solid and hollow S2-glass, T700 carbon and Tenax carbon fibres and the matrix was Ciba-Geigy MY750/HY917/DY063 epoxy mixed in the weight proportions 100:85:2. The materials were hot cured using the cycle described in Ref [2]. The tubes were wet filament wound using a progressive helical pattern with a fibre winding angle of $\pm 55^\circ$ relative to the axial direction of the tube. The tubes were typically 51mm inner diameter, 500mm long and had wall thicknesses ranging from 5 to 9.25mm. The overall length of the test specimens was typically 185mm. The ends of the specimens had additional reinforcement made of circumferentially wound E-glass/epoxy material and the gauge length was typically 75mm long. The

end reinforcement was aimed at introducing the load smoothly into the gauge length whilst avoiding premature end failure and excessive stress concentrations. The deformations of the specimens were measured using electrical strain gauges (Techni Measurement type FLA-3-23 and YFLA-2) bonded

Fig 1 A view of the high pressure cylinder with the pistons, plugs and end fittings used in the biaxial compression tests

to the inner and outer surfaces of the working section of the specimen.

2.2. Testing:

Tests on $\pm 55^\circ$ filament wound tubes were carried out under biaxial compression. The rig used for the biaxial compression tests, shown in Fig 1, consists basically of a thick cylindrical steel pressure vessel, two end threaded rings, end plugs and pistons and the test specimen. The shape of the end plugs and pistons were designed to minimise stress concentration near the tube ends. The specimens were subjected to external radial pressure with an equal end pressure that gave a nominal hoop to axial stress ratio of $SR = -2/-1$.

3. FAILURE PREDICTION

Various failure theories, including maximum stress, max strain and Tsai-Wu failure criteria[6], were used to predict failure in the tubes. The failure criteria were applied to the ply stresses which were computed using a theory for thick laminated composite tubes, see Tzeng and Chien [7].

4. RESULTS

4.1. Pressure versus strain curves

Figs 2 -6 show typical measured pressure versus hoop and axial strain for E-glass , S2-hollow glass (Hollex), S2-solid glass, T700 carbon and Tenax carbon fibre reinforced tubes. The results were obtained from several strain gauges located at different positions around the circumference, at the inside and outside surfaces, of the middle section of the

Fig 3 Pressure versus strains for a $\pm 55^\circ$ Hollex tube tested under $SR=-2/-1$. ($D=51\text{mm}$, $h=9.23\text{mm}$)

Fig 5 Pressure versus strains for a $\pm 55^\circ$ Tenax CFRP tube tested under $SR=-2/-1$ ($D=51\text{mm}$, $h=5.76\text{mm}$)

Fig 2 Pressure-strain curves for a $\pm 55^\circ$ E-GRP tube tested under $SR=-2/-1$ ($D=100\text{mm}$, $h=14.5\text{mm}$)

specimens. Superimposed on each of these figures are the theoretical predictions based on the linear elastic thick cylinder theory. In all the cases, the theoretical and experimental strains at the inside surface are larger than those at the outside surface. The difference between the slopes of axial and hoop strain depends upon the materials tested and the thickness of the cylinders. For the glass tubes, the axial strains are always smaller than the hoop strains while for the carbon the axial strains may approach the hoop strains.

Fig 4 Pressure versus strain plot for a $\pm 55^\circ$ S2-GRP tube tested under $SR=-2/-1$. ($D=51\text{mm}$, $h=6.91\text{mm}$)

Fig 6 Pressure versus strains for a $\pm 55^\circ$ T700 CFRP tube

Fig 8 Effect of thickness on the failure of 55° E-GRP tubes subjected to external pressure at $SR=-2/-1$

Fig 7 Effect of thickness on the max pressure of $\pm 55^\circ$ Hollex tubes tested under external pressure with $SR=-2/-1$.

The 5.6mm Tenax CFRP tube, shown in Fig 5 showed signs of buckling prior to final pressure where the shape of the strain curves for the individual gauges divert from their original behaviour. No thicker tubes were tested in the present work to overcome the buckling and obtain the material crushing failure for this material.

4.2. Effects of thickness on the maximum pressure

Figs 7-11 show the variation of maximum measured pressures as a function of tube thickness for the solid and hollow glass fibre tubes and for the T700 and Tenax carbon fibre tubes. In total, 8 test results (4 tests at 5.6mm and 4 at 6.88mm tube wall thickness) are shown for the solid glass fibre and 12 test results (4 tests at each of the following wall thicknesses: 5.8mm, 7mm and 9.25mm) for the hollow fibre tubes.

The measured failure pressure increased with increasing wall thickness. For the solid fibre tubes, the pressure increases from 128MPa to 161MPa as the thickness increased from 5.6 to 6.8mm. For the hollow fibres, the average maximum pressure values were 93MPa, 111MPa and 161MPa at wall thicknesses of 5.8mm, 7mm and 9.25mm, respectively. It should be noted here that all the 8 solid glass fibre tubes failed by crushing whereas the 5.8 and 7mm thick hollow fibre tubes failed by buckling. The 9.25mm thick hollow glass fibre tube did not buckle.

Superimposed on the present T700 and Tenax carbon/epoxy results are the data reported by Graham[3] for XAS and Tenax carbon/epoxy tubes for 125mm bore tubes, Figs 10 and 11. The failure pressure in present results for Tenax were higher than the Tenax carbon/epoxy tubes tested by Graham [3], indicating the latter results could have failed prematurely, either due to buckling or due other sources, although Graham did not report buckling of the thicker tubes. The failure pressure for the T700 carbon/epoxy tubes was higher than that of the XAS carbon/epoxy tubes tested by Graham[3].

Superimposed on Figs 7-11 are the theoretical failure pressures predicted by thick laminated cylinder theory using various failure theories. Each ply is under combined compressive longitudinal,

Fig 9 Effect of thickness on the failure pressure of $\pm 55^\circ$ S2-GRP tubes subjected to SR=-2/-1

compressive transverse and shear (i.e. in-plane stresses parallel and perpendicular to the fibres) and compressive through thickness stresses. The theoretical curves are shown for a number of modes of failure, namely longitudinal compression, transverse compression, through thickness compression and shear.

Using the assumed lamina strength values shown in Table 2, the E- and S2- glass/epoxy tubes are predicted to fail by transverse in-plane compression. But the experimental data seem to agree with the line indicating failure in compression along the fibre. These results show that the tubes were able to carry loads beyond those corresponding to shear and transverse compression failure.

Fig 10 Effect of thickness on the failure pressure of $\pm 55^\circ$ CFRP tubes subjected to external pressure with SR=-2/-1.

For the carbon/epoxy tubes, both test results

Fig 11 Effect of thickness on the failure pressure of $\pm 55^\circ$ CFRP tubes under SR=-2/-1.

and theoretical prediction indicate that compression along the fibres is the dominant mode of failure.

The Tsai-Wu failure theory appears to give results close to those predicted by the maximum

transverse compression results. For the glass fibre tubes, the Tsai-Wu theory under-predicted the test results while for the carbon fibre results the same theory over-predicted the test results. It was also noted that the results of the Tsai-Wu theory are sensitive to the interaction terms (K's) used in the theory. In this case, the coefficients K_{12} , K_{13} and K_{23} were taken as -0.5.

4.3. Specific properties:

Fig 12 Comparison between the Hollex and the solid S2-glass unidirectional compressive strengths

Fig 12 compares the specific strength (uniaxial compressive strength parallel to the fibres/density) of unidirectional laminae obtained from various sources for hollow and solid S2-glass composites. Boniface et al[5] and Schuster and Harman[4] reported that the specific compressive strength (strength/weight) of S2-glass/epoxy is higher than that of the Hollex. The difference was 7%, in Boniface et al results, and 39% in the Schuster and Harman [4]. DERA's results, Ref[8], however, showed that the specific strength of the hollex to be 5% higher than that of the solid glass materials. Such large differences between the compressive strengths are common also for other types of fibres, see for instance Schultheisz and Waas [9], due to, for instance, the use of different test methods and different test specimens.

Fig 13 Compressive strength of a number of metal and composite materials

Figs 13 and 14 show the absolute and specific circumferential compressive strengths, respectively, for a number of ± 55 composite tubes compared with those of metals. For the tubes of thickness 5.6-7mm, the hoop strength of the solid glass fibre tubes was around 43% higher than that of the hollow fibre tubes. However, for that range of thickness, the Hollex tubes buckled whereas the solid fibre tubes did not.

Fig 14 Specific compressive strength(strength/density) of a number of materials

If one is to compare the hoop strength of the 9.3mm Hollex tubes, which failed by crushing, with that of the 6.8mm solid fibre tubes, which also failed by crushing, the latter is just 23% higher than the former. In this case, the specific strength of the Hollex tubes is 7% superior to that of the solid glass tubes..

The results in Fig13 show that the compressive strength of all the composite tubes tested here, except that of the Hollex, were comparable with the strength of Titanium and HY130 (high performance steel). However, all the composite materials tested here including the Hollex showed superior specific strength to the metallic materials shown. The specific strength of the Tenax carbon fibre composite tube (584MPa/gr/cm³) is more than 5 times higher than the HY130 steel. The strength of the Hollex was some 2.3 times higher than that of the Titanium.

The superior specific strength of all the ± 55 tubes tested under SR=-2/-1 would decrease if the loading conditions are changed to uniaxial circumferential or axial compression. That is due to the dependency of the strength on the loading ratio. For instance, the $\pm 55^\circ$ E-glass/epoxy tubes with no axial loads had a circumferential strength of around a third of that under hydrostatic pressure (SR=-2/-1 loading), Kaddour etal[2], and hence the specific is reduced by the same amount. A similar trend is expected for the S2- hollow and solid glass and for the T700 and Tenax carbon/epoxy materials.

5. CONCLUSIONS

- It is important that a reliable testing technique be employed in order to obtain the crushing strength of composites tubes. Reported results on carbon/epoxy cylinders in the literature gave strengths almost half of those achieved in the present work.
- The thickness required to avoid buckling under hydrostatic pressure of the stiffer $\pm 55^\circ$ solid S2-

glass/epoxy tubes is observed to be smaller than that of the hollow S2-glass/epoxy tubes.

- The biaxial compressive strength of the five materials was only slightly lower than the uniaxial compressive strength of high performance metal alloy, HY130 steel.
- The specific circumferential compressive strength for the hollow S2-glass/epoxy tubes was just above that of the solid E-glass and solid S2-glass tubes.
- The carbon/epoxy tubes showed superior specific compressive strengths reaching 50% above those of the glass composites.
- The solid S2-glass/epoxy tubes showed slightly higher absolute compressive strength than the carbon and the E-glass tubes.
- The use of Tsai-Wu theory, with interaction coefficients of -0.5, for prediction of failure in the thick tubes gave conservative failure prediction in the glass tubes and un-conservative in the case of carbon fibre tubes. Although most of the crushed tubes appear to have failed due to compression along the fibre direction, a more thorough understanding is needed for failure under 3-D stress states.

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Table 1 Summary of test results for ± 55 winding angle tubes tested under hydrostatic pressure (SR=-2/-1) (All tubes were 51mm inner diameter, unless otherwise stated)

Material	Thick. mm	P_{max} MPa	$\sigma_{\theta}^{(i)}$ MPa	n	Remarks
Tenax/epoxy	5.83	143.6 \pm 7	818 \pm 26	4	
T700/epoxy	6.1	109 \pm 18.6	597 \pm 98	4	Buckling
T700/epoxy	8.3	178 \pm 7.8	768 \pm 27	4	
S2-GRP	5.66	128 \pm 5.8	773 \pm 30	4	
S2-GRP	6.88	161 \pm 6.4	841 \pm 34	4	
Hollex	5.8	92.68 \pm 6.7	548 \pm 37.3	4	Buckling
Hollex	7.1	111 \pm 11.5	573 \pm 48	4	Buckling
Hollex	9.3	161 \pm 10.8	684 \pm 46.5	4	
E-GRP*		166.84	727.7	5	

$\sigma_{\theta}^{(i)}$ Circumferential stress at the inside surface calculated from thick cylinder theory.

n: number of tests

* These were 100 and 51mm diameter tubes, see Ref[2]

Table 2. Selected Unidirectional properties of the materials used in the present work

Properties	Hollex [assumed]	S2-glass/epoxy [assumed]	T700/epoxy [assumed]	Tenax/epoxy [assumed]	E-glass/epoxy Ref[2]
E_1 GPa	40.83	62.07	138	138	50.73
E_2 GPa	11.38	22.63	8.05	8.05	19.391
G_{12} GPa	5.83	8.25	5.5	5.5	7.06
ν_{12}	0.271	0.262	0.28	0.28	0.268
ν_{23}	0.4	0.372	0.4	0.4	0.4
X_T MPa	1207	2006	1950	1950	1280
X_C MPa	750	1079	1000	1000	950
Y_T MPa	46	63	34.5	34.5	40
Y_C MPa	149	181	200	200	145
Z_T MPa	46	40	34.5	34.5	40
Z_C MPa	149	181	200	200	145
S MPa	72	72	75	75	72